

**HUMAN RIGHTS AND VALUES: INTRODUCTION,
STRUCTURE AND APPLICATION OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION
PROGRAM PROMOTING THE CONCEPTS OF "RESPONSIBILITY,
RESPECT" AND MOTOR SKILLS PERFORMANCE
IN SIX-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN**

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Abstract:

The purpose of this work was to approach and promote the concepts of responsibility and respect for children aged six years through the introduction, structure and implementation of a program that emphasized physical education. Specifically, the program included the creation of a positive learning environment with support, emotional security, and integration of non-exclusion activities, the establishment of behavioral rules, comparison to previous performance of the same ones, personalization of actions according to the children's interests, behavior feedback, maintaining of positive expectations, collaboration with all, traditional games and dances from different countries, as well as teaching to resolve disputes. Additionally, the techniques of cause- result, moral dilemma, personal view, window perspective and Socrates' dialectic method were used. Twenty-four children (13 boys, 11 girls) from a public kindergarten in the city of Ioannina participated. Prior to the implementation of the program, the parents and primary education authorities were informed and their consent was given. The program was implemented for three months in the spring of 2016 and was done twice a week for about 30 minutes. The method of the semi-structured interview was used in the initial and final assessment to approximate the concepts of respect and responsibility by children. The evaluation of the program showed that the children were initially acquainted with a few things but then they got to know even more about the value of these concepts and actions for the well-being of the wider community. The children learned to be more observative because they participated in and attended carefully the discussions and activities. They also

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approached the concepts of translations interdisciplinarily (language, literature, history, folklore, geography). Generally, they developed their motor skills, and it seemed they liked the program a lot.

Keywords: human rights, human values, respect, responsibility, motor skills, physical education, project

1. Introduction

The respect and accountability of every citizen is the basis for the practical understanding and implementation of human rights. What is important for this is the contribution of education and, above all, the spirituality of education in primary education. Preschool education is also physical-kinetic but, above all, spiritual life, which is directly related to the humanitarian principles and values that are products of rationalism. For this reason, kindergarten should educate children with these values. The procedure to make human rights a practical attitude for every citizen is long and painful.

The project improves mental development of logic mechanisms, maturation of children's motor skills, language and children's initiative (Valianza - Ears, 2013). The aim of many pre-school research was the effectiveness of the application of Experiential Communication Learning through the Project method to raise awareness and promote environmental (Zaragas, Pliogou, Mantziouka, 2016; Babila, Dimopoulou, Zombala, Frantzi, Hatzimichael, 2008) (Vassalakis, 2008), multicultural (Zaragas, Pliogou, Mantzioukas, Strati, Anagnostopoulou, 2016), health related (Koutis, Konstantinidis, Zervas, Tsaoulas, Bourcha, 2008), folkloric and natural and mathematical concepts of language and vocabulary , of the kinetic behaviour of the coeducation (George, Constantinou, 2008), the smooth transition of the child from kindergarten to elementary school (Siafarikos, Orfanopoulos, Kenourgios, Hatzimichael, 2008), against any discrimination etc. In general, the method of experiential communication and interdisciplinary approach to learning is widely used and is proposed by the modern curriculum for the Greek nursery school (DEPPS. - API, 2016). Although there are several studies that use the experiential communication and interdisciplinary approach to learning, little research in both the Greek and international contexts - especially in pre-school age - refers to promoting the concepts of accountability and respect as the basis of human rights and values.

2. Purpose

The purpose of this research was to approach and promote the concepts of accountability and respect, as well as to improve the performance of the motor skills of children aged 6 years by creating, building and implementing a physical education

program that emphasized both motor activities and the concepts of responsibility and respect.

3. Sample and method of research

The sample was randomly selected and consisted of 24 children (13 boys, 11 girls 71 ± 4 months old) of a public kindergarten in the city of Ioannina. Prior to implementing the program, parents and primary education authorities were informed and consent was subsequently given. The program was implemented for three months at the nursery premises in the spring of 2016 and was done twice a week for about 30 minutes. The method used in this research was the experiential, communicative and interdisciplinary approach of learning.

Initial Measurement	Intervention	Final Measurement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Playful activities ▪ Bloom's Taxonomy ▪ MOT - test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Three months ▪ two meetings a week for half an hour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Playful activities ▪ Taxonomy of Bloom ▪ MOT - test

Initially, the film "The Troy" was shown to children. The children, with the help of the nursery teacher, identified those points that distinguished responsibility and respect for the heroes' behavior and discussed freely expressing ideas, opinions, inspirations, thoughts, and made suggestions for these concepts with the nursery and the research team. All the children were involved in the discussion and were asked then what they would do if they were in the hero's position and how it would justify their energy, and how could we make a parallelism of the hero's actions with our everyday life in kindergarten or at home. The kindergartener with her contribution helped that the children to clarify the ideas and suggestions the children had inspired and made. The children and the research team, along with the nursery school, examined and evaluated all the suggestions and wishes that were submitted. Afterwards, decisions were made and actions - activities were planned that the children's group should perform. The activities planned for the specific period of time has been carried out and it is being experienced what have been created through the actions of the group. In the end the whole process was critically reviewed. For the performance of motor skills at the beginning and at the end of the intervention an array of 18 kinetic tests ("MOT / Motoriktest für vier-bis sechsjährige Kinder" for ages 4 to 6, Zimmer and Volkamer, 1987) was used.

The reliability analysis has shown that the internal coherence of the overall scale of motor activities has a high degree of reliability, $\alpha = 0.92$. The Kapa coefficient for the agreement of BCA between a researcher and a kindergartener is 0,88 which shows a high-level agreement.

In the context of this study, the experimental method of research was applied, taking measurements before and after the interventional method (Christensen, 2007). Prior to the beginning of the program, and at the end of its implementation, the group of children participates: a) in a semi-structured interview, the data of which allows for correlations with the dependent variables of the development and maintenance of knowledge about the concepts of responsibility and respect by children in order to control statistical changes, and (b) playful actions within a predetermined social environment (the rules of the game), children's behavioral responses (such as adherence to the rules of game) without the kindergarten teachers' urging constituted the data which allow correlations with the dependent variables of development and conservation of knowledge and application of them on the concepts of responsibility and respect. Qualitative measurements are used in the survey. In particular, in order to control the knowledge and understanding of the above conceptual concepts, the vocabulary is actually tested; a test is used in the form of a semi-structured interview protocol. The form of questions is mainly based on: (1) the analysis by Dewey (1993) of the notion of "comprehension" as "capture of meaning", consisting of finding it within objects or phenomena, and finding relationships with other phenomena or situations; and (2) the positions of Nelson (1977) and Anglin (1985), arguing that one way of assessing the changing structure of the children's vocabulary is to ask them to tell which words come to them spontaneously in response to a word or words or a question.

The questions of the interview about concepts, "man", "responsibility, I am responsible", "respect the rules", "respecting myself", "respecting the other" concern in particular: (a) the essence of the concept, what is the nature of the concept and its relation with a broader totality (social environment); (b) the characteristics and qualities of the concept (content, quality); (c) concept)with man and other beings and the environment, d) expression of emotions.

The way in which control questions are formulated, aims to obtain answers that will prove the children's acquisition of the conceptual environmental significance of the questioned words, the type of sentences they use to express themselves, the number and quality of which determines the level of development of their vocabulary and the structure of the language used. Four levels (lower than 1 ° and above 4 °) are defined, in which children are ranked according to the degree to which their vocabulary and behavioral action indicates that they have created a coherent conceptual system for each environmental word, eg:

- 1st level (grade = 0): the child does not know, does not answer either verbally or behaviorally, in any of the required concepts,
- 2nd level (grade = 1): the child knows, can answer verbally with one to three words at most for the requested meaning, and does not respond behaviorally in the game for the requested meaning, for example, does not adhere to the rules during the game,

- 3rd level (grade = 2): the child knows, can answer verbally with more than three words at most for the requested humanitarian concept, and does not respond behaviorally to the game for the environmental concept (does not respect the rules or does not respect the other's turn during the game), and
- 4th level (grade = 4): the child knows, can answer verbally with at least more than three words at about the environmental concept, and responds behaviorally to the game for the meaning sought (the child respects the rules, participates in the formation of rules and in the continuation of the game, respects and keeps the other children's turn during the game).

The criteria for classifying children at the four levels are quantitative and qualitative. A quantitative indicator is used to measure the amount of words used to answer each query. The qualitative indicator, respectively, relates to the way they use the words and the quality of the sentences to express in more comprehensible forms what they have heard and learned, answering each question with correlations, paraphrases, explanations, definitions, references, generalizations using good vocabulary. The above levels and classification criteria were based on the cognitive taxonomy of Bloom and Krathwohl (2000) according to Mechsi (2013).

The objectives of the Bloom and Krathwohl (2000) Educational Act, according to Mechsie (2013), are the partial expression of the general and specific aims of education, the delimitation of what must be provided and carried out within the classroom, the orientation in stable basis and the provision of educational purposes. These are suggestions that identify precisely what "what" students will be able to do as a result of a teaching. Bloom's taxonomy classifies the teaching objectives in three areas: a) in the cognitive field, in which the objectives related to the acquisition of knowledge and the development of mental skills and competences were ranked; b) the emotional field, in which goals relating to feelings, attitudes, beliefs and values have been included; and c) the psychomotor sector, in which they have included the objectives of developing physical skills, i.e. the implementation and coordination of various body movements.

The cognitive domain, which concerns the evaluation of our survey data, includes the following target categories:

- *Knowledge Stage*: the child remembers what he has learned, describes, repeats, recognizes, tells who, where, when, how, what.
- *Stage of Understanding*: the child describes in his own words, he expresses verbally emotions, explains concepts, compares and correlates.
- *Application stage*: the child tells how to use something, where he/she is led to, how he/she uses it to solve problems, demonstrates.
- *Stage of Analysis*: What are the parts, the order, the causes that triggered an event, the problems, the solutions, the consequences?
- *Stage of Composition*: How would it be different, how else, what would happen if, which evolution, which improvement, which progress, creativity in its own way.
- *Evaluation Stage*: How would he judge it whether or not it succeeded, if it had the effect, what he would prefer, why he thinks so.

Kindergarten children, due to their developmental characteristics, usually reach the level of "Understanding", rarely at the level of "Application" though. At the level of "Knowledge", the child memorizes and is able to recall information and knowledge in memory, to name things, terms, facts, concepts, etc. At the level of "Understanding," the child is fully conscious of what he memorized at the previous level and is able to translate it into more comprehensible verbal forms, such as to define, explain, paraphrase (to say in his own words what he has heard or seen), generalize and extend the cognitive knowledge he possesses (Matsangouras, 2002). The use of the Bloom's taxonomy (2000) was considered necessary for the descriptive analysis of the data of this research, just as it has been successfully used in other relevant scientific researches (Mechsie, 2013). The above technique is chosen because: (a) it is a reliable standardized guide used in combination with other tests, but also gives descriptive data that can help the teacher in classifying the student at one of the stages and assess the reasoning ability of the pupil's critical thinking and maturity; b) Bloom's taxonomy does not define specific ages in which the child must have reached a stage to be considered competent. The learner is guided to learn ways to express his / her thoughts about a subject verbally (and in writing) from the simplest way of expression which is Bloom's stage of "Knowledge" up to the most complex and critical stage of this "Assessment".

In the specific research, in each question, the corresponding statement, is considered as: *He does not know* when the child does not use any word, which is a true feature of the humanitarian concept of the word (responsibility, respect), and is ranked in the 1st level, the child uses one to one word, which is a true feature of the concept of the word, and is ranked in the 2nd level, *Inadequate*, when he uses or associates two to three words, and is ranked in the 3rd level, *correct / complete* when used he speaks from four words and up and can say, paraphrase (to say in his own words what he hears or sees), to define, to explain, to generalize, using the appropriate vocabulary, consequently in this case he is ranked on the 4th level, as shown in the following table "2".

Lower level ratings, e.g. can be attributed to more words, since they work to show the quality of the meaning of the words. The level is ranked by the quantitative indicator. The quantitative indicator is used to measure the amount of sentences before and after the program implementation.

Table 2: Frequency recording protocol according to the ranking levels of the children's responses for the humanitarian concepts of "accountability" and "respect" based on the cognitive approach of Bloom & Krathwohl (2000).

RANKING LEVELS OF ANSWERS	1 TH LEVEL DOESN'T KNOW	2 ND LEVEL KNOWLEDGE	3 RD LEVEL COMPREHENSION	4 TH LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION
CHARACTERISTICS OF REPLIES	No words	Answers in one word	Answers in two to three words	Answers with four words and more, while at the same time applies the corresponding action of the semantic content of the words in practice.
CONTENT	Definitions, References, declarations	Definitions, References, declarations	Explanations, Correlations, Paraphrasing, Findings, comparisons	Generalizations, predictions
SKOR	Zero (0)	ONE (1)	TWO (2)	THREE (3)

3.1 The interview and game in a guided environment for the collection of research data

Based on the experiences, the contact and the knowledge about the area of preschool age and these children's language skills, the draft of the semi-structured interview was designed with the help of which we seek to answer our research questions, gathering, evaluating data on the development of the children's words, phrases (linguistic) related to the concepts of accountability and respect. The interview is probably the most widely used method of pumping quality material and information in the social sciences (Kambitsis, 2004).

Questions (target: vocabulary, understanding, and semantic analysis of humanitarian concepts "accountability" and "respect") are indicatively as follows:

- Do you know what "responsibility" is?
- Do you know what "man" means?
- Do you know what "I am responsible, I have a responsibility" means?
- Do you know what it means to "takes care of being clean"?
- Do you know what it means "I do not dirty the space (home, kindergarten)"?
- Do you know what it means to "do not bother others"?
- Do you know what it means to "I am careful to arrange my toys"?
- Do you know what it means "I am a team leader"?
- Do you know what it means "I am the assistant to the team leader"?
- Do you know what it means "I am an assistant to the teacher"?
- Do you know what "respect" is?
- Do you know what "I respect the game, the rules of the game"?
- Do you know what "I respect children"?
- Do you know what "do I respect the teacher" mean?
- Do you know what it means "I respect the other who has a different look from me (black, Chinese, Albanian, Pakistani, fat)"?
- Do you know what "I admire the teacher" means?
- Do you know what "I admire my friends" means?
- How many things can you do to be responsible?

- How many things can you do when you respect others?
- Would you play in the same team with a kid who does not manage well as you do in football?
- What do others do when they respect you?
- What comes to mind when you hear the word "do I respect the children from a foreign country"?
- Can you name the actions you make when playing with your friends?
- Can you name the moves you make when playing with your friends?
- How do you feel when you play with your friends and they cheer you up?
- How do you feel when you play with your friends and they spoil the game?
- How would you feel if your friends did not play you?
- In what ways can you show how happy you are?
- In what ways can you show that you are responsible?
- In what ways can you show that you respect others?
- When you hear the word "lake" what things come to your mind?
- When our nursery teacher says: "we are responsible for keeping the yard clean", what should we do?
- What would you do if you were playing with a child who does not manage as well as you?
- How do you imagine the game with your friends?

The control activities (the objective of implementing humanitarian actions referring to accountability and respect), as distinguished through the children's free play, are as follows:

- Courtyard cleaning, from various objects found completely accidentally thrown into the yard of the nursery school and hindering children's sports activities. The children first cleared the yard voluntarily, not after the nursery's encouragement, and then carried out the sporting activities that were planned.
- The children immediately after playing in the yard of the kindergarten washed their hands with soap and shook their dirty clothes from sand and greens.
- The children participated in the formation of the rules of the game.
- Children applied and adhered to the rules of the games they had formed.
- After a visit to a park and toys and sports activities, the children cleaned and arranged the discarded objects (paper, plastic, etc.) in special baskets on their own.

3.2 Identifying the right answers and the limitations to the questions of the children's interviews

The questions of the interview concern the notions of "man, responsibility, I am responsible, I respect the rules, I respect myself, I respect the other". They refer, initially, to the deeper meaning of these concepts, as well as to their relations with a wider totality (social environment) (Dewey, 1933). At the second level, the physical characteristics and qualities of each concept (form, shape, situation) are sought (Anglin, 1985) and at the final level the meaning of each concept separately, as well as its relation

to other concepts (Nelson, 1977). In this way, the answers to both the interview questions and activities are identified as correct or incorrect, when it is proven or not, the finding of the essentials in the objects or phenomena, or the identification of the properties and relationships between the objects or phenomena by the student.

More specifically,

Question 1: Responsibility

All words relating to the attributes of responsibility are taken as correct and measurable answers (I know how not to spoil the game, my mom left me responsible for taking care of my toys and keeping my room clean, we are responsible for being clean and washing our hands after the game, the teacher told us that we have to be responsible and be careful not to get hurt in the yard, we pass the road under our own responsibility) size properties (big, small), emotional descriptions (it's right, I love to care about my room, I know my responsibilities when I play with other children, I take care of my toys not to damage them, I care for my body, I wash my hands after the game, I wash my teeth after eating, I make sure that I do not spoil the children's game when I do not want to go on. They are not counted as the correct words the ones regarding the repetition of the question (responsibility).

During the intervention, children are shown and involved in role-playing and discussion (moral dilemma) regarding responsibility both individually and collectively. Cleaning the yard was combined before and after games and sports. Participatory observation was used to collect the data. For the recording of the data during the intervention, observation sheets, as well as the children's work were used.

Activities

The criterion was to keep children's interest in active, enthusiastic participation and it was this that had determined the choice of activities. The objectives set and the activities carried out are presented below.

A. In the field of Creation and Expression: Physical education

Goals:

- The development of kinetic behavior through the development of physical activity,
- Promotion of visual / acoustic / tactile / mobile coordination, assembling skills, and motor skills
- Obtaining and observing the rules,
- The appropriate use of educational material and the development of positive attitudes for communication, cooperation, mutual acceptance and support, movement.

Activities:

- They played chasing the ball, football, small wallet, relay races in the yard.
- They danced with ribbons, circles or pairs, dances, and everyone improvised as they wanted.
- They created small potholes in a specially shaped area by digging with small plastic shovels after having properly and equally shared the space.

- They played in the yard variations of traditional toy-toe-game and "bee passes", called to choose between the stork and the eel.
- They sang music songs and danced.
- They built houses in the yard and buildings with plastic bricks.
- Using the sticks of the psychomotor sector, they played the game of "driver and passenger" in pairs of quadrants but also the whole team: each pair held a ribbon and the child who was a "guide" was leading the child-passenger, pulling it with the ribbon. Then the roles were changed, while in a variation of the game the passenger had his eyes closed with a cloth.

B. In the field of Creation and Expression: Art

Goals:

- Developing imagination and creativity,
- Cultivation of visual and tactile perception,
- Observation, experimentation, research and use of experiences as elements of artistic creation and expression,
- Practicing the use of material and various techniques for acquiring skills and encouraging the production of works of art,
- Understanding art as a means of expression and communication.

Activities:

- We made a model of the earth using a ball of blue, black, green, yellow and red wafers and plasticine in different colors for the five continents of the earth.
- We built tables and mirrors that depicted the hygiene rules and areas of cleanliness of each group.
- We painted children and parents from other countries with markers, oil paints and watercolors.
- We made the flag of the Olympic Games with the five rounds.
- We built medals with clay and, when dried, we painted them with markers.
- We made the "ketone" olive branch, using cardboard and plasticine.
- With the technique of collage, we created mosaics on dance, kite.
- A group of children painted people with different characteristics (color, disability, age, gender) and cut them, the second one made a beautiful urban landscape (houses, square, park) with plasticine, and the third one painted mountains, birds and the sun in the cardboard using temperas and in the end all together the groups created a composition on the harmonious coexistence of people.

C. In the field of Creation and Expression: Dramatic Art

Goals:

- Express themselves through dramatic play and imitation
- Exercise their linguistic and expressive ability through the processing of literary texts
- Collaborate and create together
- To select and use creatively various materials useful in dramatic art

- Cultivate their aesthetic expression and creation.

Activities:

- We've dramatized quotations from fairy tales and stories that we used in the program. The scenes were chosen by the children from "Aesop's Tales", and "Triangle little fish". The children built, painted the heroes in cardboard and played the heroes playing a puppet show.
- They played on the theme of "respect": they were divided into groups and the children imitated the ways of expressing themselves during their encounter with older people than they were, on the road, at home, on the bus.
- They dramatized the way of the kindergartener's behavior in the kindergarten, the leaders of a football team, the firefighters' in extinguishing a fire, the police's in action.

D. In the field of Creation and Expression: Music

Goals:

- Develop skills that, by playing various musical instruments and by singing, they can perform their own compositions
- Respond to symbols, slogans and instructions
- Present their performances
- Improvising and expressing through simple music
- Get acquainted with different kinds of music, eg, traditional, artistic, and classical.

Activities:

- We listened to music, we sang songs about people, animals, and some of these children used motions too.
- Separated into groups of black, white, red and yellow people, they made an orchestra with the conductor each time changing to represent all the colors.
- Each group chose from the musical instruments those ones that they would represent: the black ones chose the debris, the red pearl the maracas, the yellow the bells and the white the scraper. The conductor defined who will play first, who the next and when they will all play together.

E. In the field of Language

Goals:

- Encouragement of narration, explanation, interpretation of children's personal experiences or literary texts (Aesop's Myths, Stories of Ancient Olympic Games).
- Participate in discussions in accordance with the rules and the order of discussion.
- Developing elementary arguments by children to justify their own views.
- Awareness of the oral-written relationship and enrichment of spoken word by using purposeful words, phrases, idioms, etc.

Activities:

- We have read fairy tales, poems and stories to the children, turning the book towards them, so that they realize that what is being read is text, not the picture.

- We asked questions about the development of the story and the understanding of the text.
- From the fairy tale we have read, the children distinguished words they liked and made sentences with them which they dictated for us to write them on a reference table.
- They also tried to copy words they liked from the fairy tale.
- As far as the writing is concerned, during the visit to the park, the children, with the chopsticks they found there, formed the five rounds of the Olympic Flag.
- During their visit to the environmental park of the lake, they wrote their names on the notebook.
- The children brought from home stories, proverbs relative to the subject, wrote and read them.
- Language and writing were also cultivated through activities of all the fields across the program.

E. In the field of Mathematics

Goals:

- Developing the ability to perceive certain properties, relationships and associative elements from the surrounding world
- Comparing and transforming relationships and processes with testing and checking
- Applying familiar mathematical structures to new situations
- Expanding of the children's first mathematical knowledge through experiential situations.

Activities:

- We gave the children little people, animals, trees from cardboard canson in various sizes (large, small, wide, narrow), which they ranked and put in order from the largest to the smallest ones and vice versa.
- We played the group game "the shephard and the sheep": we distributed small cards with sheep in different sizes to children. The children ran freely in the room, and when the shepherd called out signals, for example, "little ones" all the children who had a small sheep cartel were running around him.
- They made little people with plasticine, made classifications by color, measured and placed the number tab.

G. In the field of Environmental Study: Natural Environment

Goals:

- Expand their knowledge of the natural environment (fauna, flora)
- Expand their knowledge of animal organisms
- Enhance their knowledge of plant organisms
- To experiment with the properties of water, color, taste, with concepts of submerges - floats with the phenomenon of buoyancy
- Expand their knowledge on the relationship between air-water-earth-human.
- Enhance their knowledge of responsible environmental attitudes and behavior

Activities:

- We gave children books about life in the city, the village, the countryside, and then followed a debate and they painted what they liked it.
- They were shown DVDs related to water, forest and water and discussion followed. We visited, respectively, the lake, the springs and the forest where the children were constantly asking questions about the games.

H. In the field of Environmental Study: Anthropogenic Environment

Goals:

- To broaden the children's social environment, while developing their self-esteem and critical thinking.
- Develop co-operation skills.
- Understand the interaction between the natural environment and the human being.
- To broaden their knowledge of their individual attitudes and behavior regarding discrimination to others.

Activities:

- We visited the environmental park, primary school, playground, museum, town hall and we used these visits as a field of action and observation.
- The children discussed at the end of each visit to the above-mentioned locations for human presence and how decisive it was to create positive and negative impacts.
- We discussed with the children what could be done by both adults and children to preserve the beauty of the place. We also took a series of actions on the occasion of the World Day for both the Environment and the Olympic Games.
- The dissemination of our program to the wider local community took place with the final feast and exhibition of the constructions that were built by the children during the program.

I. In the field of Information Technology

Goal:

- To understand the computer as a machine that helps people in their work
- Identify its main units (keyboard, desktop, mouse) and computer as a single system
- To develop activities in the context of a variety of group and composite work
- Understand the impact of new technologies on the different areas of human activity.

Activities:

- The children played electronic games with the help of corresponding software programs. Then there was a discussion about what they liked and what impressed them.
- Then the children painted with the help of the mouse on the computer.
- Later on the children wrote letters, words with the help of the «mouse» of the computer.

4. Statistical analysis

The non-parametric statistical analysis "Friedman test" was made for the difference in performance between initial and final measurements in Bloom's classification for the concepts of the survey.

In order to assess the statistical significance of the differences that can be identified between the initial and final measurements for both the performance of motor skills (kinetic behavior) and the concepts of "responsibility and respect" too, the associated "t" control was used.

A Cronbach internal validity index was 0.89 which showed that the twenty control activities (questions, games) used for the initial and final measurement were reliable and that they actually measured what was the research object of the research. The Kappa coefficient for the agreement between the researchers in this survey is 0.68 which shows a high level agreement.

5. Results of the survey

5.1 For rendering motor skills

The children, according to the scores they accomplished, are classified according to the instructions of the manufacturers of the MTT - test in various categories (very good, well, normal, under normal and kinetic difficulties), as distinguished by the following table "4". It is noted that in the initial control tests a child (4.2%) seems to have a lower kinetic performance while the rest ones (N = 23, 95.8%) achieve normal performance for their age. In the final measurements, it appears that the intervention program helped both this child – whose performance in the initial measurements was below the normal level - to achieve normal performance as well as a group of children (N = 8, 33.3%), to achieve better and more improved performance than their original one.

Table 3: Classification of the children's motor performance in both the initial and final measurement (N=24,100.00%) in eighteen motor activities, MOT games-test

CLASSIFICATION LEVELS MOT -test	LIMITS	INITIAL MEASUREMENT		FINAL MEASUREMENT	
		F	%	f	%
VERY WELL	34				
WELL	33 - 28			8	33,3
NORMAL	27 - 14	23	95,8	16	66,7
BELOW NORMAL	13 - 9	1	4,2		
KINETIC DIFFICULTIES	8 <				
TOTAL		24	100,00	24	100,00

5.2 For the concepts of accountability and respect

Five control questions and five games were applied to each concept. In Table 5 in general, it appears that in the initial tests there is a large concentration of responses in the "do not know" category and few in the "application" category, which in the final

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measurements and after the intervention changes with zero concentrations of answers in the category "do not know "And too many in the application category.

The average performance of motor skills in the initial pre-intervention control tests (mean = 22.42 & TA = 3.90, see table "3") and the average in the final post-test differ significantly ($t = -17,564$, $df = 23$, $p = 0.001$, see table "3").

Table 4: Frequencies and percentages for the performance of the sample (N = 24, 100%) in both questions and games for knowledge, understanding and application of the notions of "respect" and "responsibility", in pre-test and final post-intervention testing.

QUESTIONS & GAMES	INITIAL MEASUREMENT										FINAL MEASUREMENT									
	DON'T KNOW		KNOW		COMPRE-HENSION		APPLI-CATION		N	DON'T KNOW		KNOW		COMPRE-HENSION		APPLI-CATION		N		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		f	%	f	%	f	%					
QUESTIONS OF RESPONSIBILITY	1 ^H	15	12,5	3	2,5	2	1,7	4	3,3	24					5	4,2	19	15,8	24	
	2 ^H	14	11,7	5	4,2	2	1,7	3	2,5	24				6	5	18	15	24		
	3 ^H	11	9,2	3	2,5	5	4,2	5	4,2	24				3	2,5	21	17,5	24		
	4 ^H	9	7,5	6	5	4	3,3	5	4,2	24	3	2,5	5	4,2	16	13,5	24	24		
	5 ^H	10	8,3	7	5,8	3	2,5	4	3,3	24	2	1,7	7	5,8	15	12,5	24	24		
	TOTAL	59	49,2	24	20,0	16	13,5	21	17,5	120					5	4,2	26	21,7	89	74,1
QUESTIONS OF RESPECT	1 ^H	18	15	3	2,5	1	0,8	2		24	6	5	9	7,5	9	7,5	24	24		
	2 ^H	15	12,5	6	5	2	1,7	1		24	4	3,3	11	9,2	9	7,5	24	24		
	3 ^H	19	15,8	2	1,7	3	2,5			24	7	5,8	9	7,5	8	6,7	24	24		
	4 ^H	21	17,5	2	1,7	1	0,8			24	3	2,5	8	6,7	13	10,8	24	24		
	5 ^H	24	20							24	6	5	11	9,2	7	5,8	24	24		
	TOTAL	97	80,8	13	10,8	7	5,8	3	2,5	120	26	21,7	48	40	46	38,3	120	100		
TOTAL OF QUESTIONS	156	65	37	15,5	23	9,5	24	10	240	31	13	74	31	135	56	240	100			
GAMES OF RESPONSIBILITY	1 ^H	16	13,5	4	3,3	2	1,7	2	1,7	24				10	8,3	14	11,7	24		
	2 ^H	13	10,8	5	4,2	2	1,7	4	3,3	24				11	9,2	13	10,8	24		
	3 ^H	12	10	4	3,3	5	4,2	3	2,5	24	3	2,5	8	6,7	13	10,8	24	24		
	4 ^H	8	6,7	6	5	5	4,2	5	4,2	24	1	0,8	6	5	17	14,2	24	24		
	5 ^H	11	9,2	7	5,8	3	2,5	3	2,5	24				10	8,3	14	11,7	24		
	TOTAL	60	50,0	26	21,6	17	14,2	17	14,2	120	4	3,30	45	37,5	71	59,20	120	100		
GAMES OF RESPECT	1 ^H	16	13,5	3	2,5	2	1,7	3	2,5	24	4	3,3	8	6,7	12	10	24	24		
	2 ^H	16	13,5	2	1,7	2	1,7	4	3,3	24	4	3,3	7	5,8	13	10,8	24	24		
	3 ^H	14	11,7	6	5	1	0,8	3	2,5	24	3	2,5	9	7,5	12	10	24	24		
	4 ^H	18	15	2	1,7	2	1,7	2	1,7	24	4	3,3	6	5	14	11,7	24	24		
	5 ^H	15	12,5	4	3,3	1	0,8	4	3,3	24	4	3,3	7	5,8	13	10,8	24	24		
	TOTAL	79	65,6	17	14,2	8	6,7	16	13,5	120	19	15,8	37	30,8	64	53,4	120	100		
TOTAL OF GAMES	139	58	43	18	25	10,5	33	13,5	240	23	9,6	82	34,2	135	56,2	240	100			
TOTAL OF QUESTIONS AND GAMES	295	61,5	80	17	48	10	57	11,5	480	54	11,2	156	32,5	270	56,3	480	100			

TABLE 5: average, standard deviation, and the correlation control «t», of the scores achieved by children (N= 24, 100,00%) in the total of ten activities (questions – games) for the «responsibility and respect»

	RESPONSIBILITY		RESPECT	
	BEGINNING	END	BEGINNING	END
AVERAGE	19,58	36,71	14,88	32,71
STANDARD DEVIATION	10,85	2,61	8,06	7,15
<i>t</i>	-16,35		-13,58	
<i>df</i>	47		47	
<i>P</i> _{DOUBLE TAIL}	0,001		0,001	

Graphic depiction 1: Answers to both questions and games about the concepts of respect and responsibility of children in the sample (N = 24, 100.00%).

6. Discussion Conclusions and Evaluation

However, this study has attempted at even younger ages than elementary school, particularly in preschool children aged five and six, and this is exactly the innovative element. The research questions as it were whether the children involved in the intervention would actually promote the concepts of accountability and respect. In particular, the concepts of "responsibility, I am responsible, I respect the rules, I respect myself, respect the other", and even if it will promote the kinetic performance of children through the implementation of the intervention.

The initial performance of Bloom's cognitive classification of responsibility and respect showed that the children were barely aware and practicing, for example when you have been assigned as a head assistant or a leader to know what to do, not to take the turn from another child, to play, to keep the room clean after playing, not to reject another child due to reduced motor performance, when the teacher assigns you to be responsible for something to know what you have to do, etc. The final trials showed that children have understood and applied the conditions of responsibility (individual and social) and respect in the game.

The executive function refers to the child's ability to perform appropriate measures and to inhibit inappropriate actions to achieve a goal (Dempster, 1992; Anderson, 2002; Diamond, 2002; Zelazo, et al., 2003; Durston, Davidson, Tottenham, et al., 2006; Moriguchi, 2014, 388). Research has shown that executive capacity is growing rapidly at pre-school age.

Koymen, Schmidt, Rust, Lieven, and Tomasello (2015) conclude that preschool children aged 3 years are able to communicate effectively and appropriately through the application of the rules of the game interact - depending on the level of knowledge rules of play - with peers.

This intervention is considered to be entirely successful because the goal set at the beginning of the program has been reached at a knowledge level with children not only knowing, understanding but also applying as best as they can the responsibility and respect (individually, socially) and comprehending the role of these concepts in shaping relationships between people.

This intervention is considered to be entirely successful because the goal set at the beginning of the program was also achieved at an emotional level, by developing the critical thinking of the child, developing the interest in responsibility and respect (individually, socially), understanding the role of these concepts in shaping people-to-people relationships, encouraging children to apply individual responsibility and respect to the game, encouraging children to take decisions to deal with discrimination in the game.

The success of intervention in the psycho-motoring sector was not only limited to improving motor skills, but also to the fact that children learned during the game to observe the other children's attitudes regarding responsibility and respect and to distinguish these behaviors. They expressed their feelings with paintings and role playing too.

The children collaborated in groups and also had the opportunity to develop excellent interpersonal relationships outside the boundaries of the kindergarten. The children's interest and their engagement with experiential exploration and experimentation activities remained at a high level until the end of the program. Their physical and athletic activities were performed well; their works in the visual arts were of high quality and also showed great skill and talent in drama and theatrical plays. They cultivated their critical thinking and active listening that is essential for the healthy socialization of the individual.

The results of this research could be important for kindergarteners who want to develop the concepts of responsibility and respect for physical education programs. Through active participation of children in sport activities (not purely sporting) and their awareness on ethical and social issues, significant social, emotional and social benefits could be achieved, both in terms of children's personality and the wider society and community. Also, the findings of this research could be a stimulus for the future design of educational programs by nursery teachers for social issues related to Olympism and the Olympic Ideals.

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A PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAM PROMOTING THE CONCEPTS OF "*RESPONSIBILITY, RESPECT*"
AND MOTOR SKILLS PERFORMANCE IN SIX-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN

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